

Synthesis and characterization of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 2,14-dimethyl-3,15-di-*n*-propyl-1,4,13,16-tetraazacyclotetracos-1,3,13,15-tetraene

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Abstract : Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of a 24-membered tetraazamacrocyclic, 2,14-dimethyl-3,15-di-*n*-propyl-1,4,13,16-tetraazacyclotetracos-1,3,13,15-tetraene, have been prepared by 2+2 cyclocondensation of 2,3-hexanedione and 1,8-diaminooctane in the presence of metal ions as templates. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductances, IR spectra, magnetic measurements and ¹H NMR spectra.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes, magnetic moments, IR spectra.

Introduction

Due to their biological relevance, transition metal complexes of a variety of tetraazamacrocycles derived from α - or β -diketones have been synthesized and a large number of Cr^{III}, Fe^{II}, Co^{III}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of 13 to 16-membered tetraazamacrocycles have been reported¹⁻⁹. However, the complexes of large ring tetraazamacrocycles have not been studied systematically so far. In continuation of our earlier work on Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 22-, 26- and 28-membered tetraazamacrocycles^{10,11} we report herein the synthesis and characterization of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of a 24-membered macrocycle, 2,14-dimethyl-3,15-di-*n*-propyl-1,4,13,16-tetraazacyclotetracos-1,3,13,15-tetraene (L, Fig. 1) derived from 2,3-hexanedione and 1,8-diaminooctane.

Fig. 1. 2,14-Dimethyl-3,15-di-*n*-propyl-1,4,13,16-tetraazacyclotetracos-1,3,13,15-tetraene (L).

Experimental

Materials : Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (Fluka), Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (Fluka), Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (Fluka), Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (Merck), CuCl₂·2H₂O (BDH), ZnCl₂ (Fluka), 2,3-hexanedione (Aldrich) and 1,8-diaminooctane (Merck) were used as supplied. *n*-Butanol was distilled before use.

Analytical methods : Chromium was determined volumetrically by potassium dichromate using diphenylamine as indicator. Similarly, the iron content was also determined in the Fe^{III} complex as Fe^{II} after its reduction with stannous chloride. Copper was determined iodometrically using starch as indicator. Cobalt, nickel and zinc were determined volumetrically by EDTA using xylenol orange indicator for cobalt and eriochrome black T for nickel and zinc. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Chlorine was determined gravimetrically as AgCl. Carbon and hydrogen analyses were carried out on a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 instrument. IR spectra of KBr pellets of the samples were recorded in the region 4000–400 cm⁻¹ on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. Specific conductances were measured at room temperature in DMSO by a 304 Systronics direct reading conductivity meter. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as calibrant. ¹H NMR spectrum was recorded in DMSO-d₆

on a Bruker 300 NMR spectrometer using TMS as a reference.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes : $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.0 mmol, 0.4002 g) was dissolved in ~20 mL *n*-butanol and 2.0 mmol (0.2283 g) of 2,3-hexanedione (in ~15 mL of *n*-butanol) was added. A solution of 1,8-diaminooctane (2.0 mmol, 0.2885 g in ~15 mL *n*-butanol) was added dropwise with constant stirring. Stirring was continued for ~5 h. The solid product obtained was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Reactions of $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and ZnCl_2 with 2,3-hexanedione and 1,8-diaminooctane were carried out using similar procedure.

Results and discussion

Reactions of metal salts with 2,3-hexanedione and 1,8-diaminooctane in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratios result in the formation of metal complexes of a 24-membered tetraazamacrocycle (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes.

The resulting macrocyclic complexes are coloured solids and do not melt but decompose on heating at higher temperatures (Table 1). They are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as methanol, acetone, carbon tetra-

chloride and chloroform but soluble in dimethyl sulfoxide. All the complexes gave satisfactory elemental analyses. The analyses and characteristics of these complexes are recorded in Table 1.

Eggleston and Jackels¹² have ruled out the possibility of the formation of 1 + 1 condensation products, such as diazepine (Fig. 2), during the template synthesis of Fe^{II} , Co^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes of 2,9-dimethyl-3,10-diphenyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene, on the basis of ¹H NMR studies.

Fig. 2. Diazepine.

Infrared spectra : Absorption bands at 1580–1625 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the stretching vibrations of the coordinated C=N group, confirming the formation of the azomethine linkage^{13,14}. The complexes of Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} show a characteristic absorption band at 1015–1040 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to a coordinated nitrate group and the appearance of absorption bands at 1470–1550 cm^{-1} confirms the monodentate coordination mode of the nitrate group^{15,16}. Nitrate complexes of Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} also exhibit absorption bands at 1375–1380 and 810–825 cm^{-1} which can be attributed to the ionic nitrate. Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of macrocycles derived from dihydrazide and aromatic diketones have been reported to exhibit characteristic bands at ~1350, 1230 and 825 cm^{-1} due to ionic nitrate¹⁷. In the IR spectra of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, appearance of absorption bands due to coordinated as well as ionic nitrate indicates that the nitrate groups are weakly coordinated supporting distorted octahedral geometry.

Conductances : Molar conductances of 10^{-3} M solutions of the complexes in DMSO are recorded in Table 1. Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes behave as 3 : 1 electrolytes indicating that the coordinated nitrate groups are replaced by the solvent molecules. Molar conductances ~109 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ in DMSO have been reported for 3 : 1

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of metal complexes of the macrocycle Me₂Pr₂[24]N₄tetraene (L)^a

Complex	Colour and temp. of decomp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analyses (%) : Found/(Calcd.)					Molar cond. (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	μ _{eff} (BM)
			C	H	M	N	Cl		
[CrL(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Light grey	94	49.02	7.74	7.54	8.31	-	119	4.24
	163		(49.26)	(7.67)	(7.61)	(8.20)			
[FeL(NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Brown	77	48.74	7.75	8.15	8.22	-	102	6.10
	130		(48.98)	(7.63)	(8.13)	(8.16)			
[CoL(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	42	53.35	8.40	9.43	8.82	-	94	4.96
	150		(53.58)	(8.35)	(9.39)	(8.92)			
[NiL(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	32	53.41	8.43	9.29	8.87	-	60	4.06
	240		(53.60)	(8.36)	(9.35)	(8.93)			
[CuL]Cl ₂	Light green	43	57.81	9.12	10.86	9.72	12.14	74	2.06
	166		(58.06)	(9.05)	(10.97)	(9.67)	(12.24)		
[ZnL]Cl ₂	Light yellow	43	57.62	9.10	11.35	9.59	12.10	13.6	Diamagnetic
	212		(57.88)	(9.02)	(11.25)	(9.64)	(12.20)		

^aThe N values do not include nitrate nitrogen which is removed on treatment with H₂SO₄ in Kjeldahl's method.

electrolytes¹⁸. The conductance values for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes correspond to 2 : 1 electrolytes indicating that both nitrate groups are replaced by solvent molecules. Cu^{II} complex also behaves as 2 : 1 electrolyte¹⁹. The molar conductance of the Zn^{II} complex is very low showing it to be a non-electrolyte¹⁸.

Magnetic moments : The complexes of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} show magnetic moments 4.24²⁰, 6.10¹⁵, 4.96²¹, 4.06²² and 2.06 BM⁵ respectively (Table 1). Higher values of magnetic moments for Cr^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes may be due to orbital contribution and distortion from regular octahedral geometry²³. The Zn^{II} complex is diamagnetic.

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectra : ¹H NMR spectrum of the Zn^{II} complex is reproduced in Fig. 3. The α-CH₂ protons of the amine residue give a triplet at δ 2.57 ppm due to coupling with the β-CH₂ protons. The β-CH₂ protons of the amine residue appear as a broad peak at δ 1.40 ppm. A broad peak at δ 1.18 ppm is observed due to γ-CH₂ and other remaining methylene protons. In the free diamine the α-CH₂ protons give a triplet at δ 2.69 ppm whereas the β-CH₂ protons appear as a quintet at δ 1.33 ppm²⁴. In free macrocycle, though not isolated, these peaks would have appeared at lower field, e.g. for the

macrocyclic precursor, 1,2,8,9-tetraphenyl-3,7-diazaduohepta-2,7-diene-1,9-dione (KIM, Fig. 4) a triplet at δ 3.63 ppm due to α-CH₂ and a quintet at δ 2.11 ppm due to β-CH₂ protons have been observed⁴.

In the macrocyclic complex of Zn^{II} these peaks are expected to shift upfield due to the coordination of the >C=N- group of the macrocycle to the metal atom. Thus the upfield shift of these protons (α- and β-CH₂) confirms the coordination of the nitrogen atoms of the macrocycle to the zinc atom. Free diamine shows a peak at δ 1.15 ppm due to the -NH₂ protons, which disappears in the macrocyclic complexes confirming the condensation of the -NH₂ groups of the amine residue with the >C=O groups of the ketone residue to give macrocycles having >C=N linkages. The ketone residue of the macrocyclic complex shows a singlet at δ 1.70 ppm due to CH₃^d protons. The CH₃^a protons of *n*-propyl group of 2,3-hexanedione residue give a triplet at δ 0.80 ppm due to coupling with the CH₂^b protons. A broad peak appears at δ 1.98 ppm due to the CH₂^c protons of the ketone residue. The peaks due to CH₂^b protons of the ketone residue merge with the peaks of CH₂ protons (γ and others) of the amine residue. Thus the NMR data support the proposed structure of the macrocyclic complex.

Fig. 3. ^1H NMR spectrum of $[\text{Zn}(\text{Me}_2\text{Pr}_2)_2(\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Cl}_2]$.

Fig. 4. 1,2,8,9-Tetraphenyl-3,7-diazaduohepta-2,7-diene-1,9-dione.

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